

THE EFFECT OF TESTING TEMPERATURE ON CAVITATION IN DISCONTINUOUS MMCs DURING TENSILE STRAINING

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ABSTRACT

The formation of cavities during tensile straining of discontinuously reinforced MMCs has been studied over a range of test temperatures, using densitometry and microstructural examinations. The onset of cavitation is delayed on increasing the temperature, presumably due to increased plasticity of the matrix. At higher temperatures necking starts to occur at lower strains, the necked region soon becoming unstable and resulting in lower strains to failure. This suggests that void stability is reduced with increased test temperature. On raising the temperature, the favoured void formation sites change from interfaces with flat areas normal to the applied load to those exhibiting sharp corners pointing along the stress axis.

Keywords: MMC, cavitation, tensile test, elevated temperature, interfaces, reinforcement shape, volume fraction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Failure in discontinuously reinforced MMCs is often associated with the formation and growth of voids at the reinforcement/matrix interface¹⁻³, which subsequently coalesce by ductile tearing. Finite element calculations based on elastic deformation^{4,5} have shown that a high hydrostatic tension will be generated in the matrix adjacent to the reinforcing particles, along the line of applied stress, particularly when the interface is normal to the stress axis and is relatively wide in the transverse direction. These will therefore be regions where cavitation is expected. It has been established that the onset of cavitation will be dependent on the local stress state around the reinforcing particle⁶. It is therefore likely that the reinforcement shape will have a direct influence on the cavitation characteristics of the composite. Previous work^{7,8} at room temperature has established that stable voids can exist well before failure in these materials, and has shown that cavitation is favoured by reinforcement with flat surfaces aligned normal to the applied stress.

Cavitation and ductility will also be affected by the nature of the interfacial bond, and the ductility of the matrix. The strength of the interfacial bond is expected to affect the load bearing capacity of the composite, and the ease with which cavitation and other stress relaxation processes can occur. Finite element calculations⁴ suggest that cavitation will occur more easily as the interfacial bond strength is decreased. While there are few experimental data characterising this effect, it has

been suggested⁹ that a reduction in the interfacial bond strength in AlSiC_p composites, by alloying with Mg, significantly increases the ductility, while reducing the work hardening rate. However, it is unclear how this affects cavitation processes in these materials.

While there has been extensive study of (steady state) creep¹⁰⁻¹² of discontinuously reinforced composites, relatively little work has been carried out on tensile properties and failure mechanisms at elevated temperature. Previous research on the subject has concentrated simply on characterising the strength of composite at elevated temperatures^{13,14}. An understanding of the mechanisms of failure is required in order to optimise the high temperature strength and creep rupture resistance.

The extent of cavitation will be influenced by the potential for alternative stress relaxation processes. As the testing temperature is increased, both matrix plasticity and diffusional stress relaxation mechanisms become easier. This is expected to alter the cavitation characteristics. Previous work by Furness¹² into cavitation during creep suggested that at high temperature favoured cavitation sites may be the angularities of reinforcement particles. However, previous room temperature tensile work^{7,8,15} has shown that flattish surfaces normal to the stress axis, rather than angularities, are the favoured sites. In the present paper the effect of testing temperature on cavitation has been investigated for composites containing different volume fractions of three reinforcements having different shapes. In addition, the effect of matrix oxide content has been investigated by comparing results from powder-route and cast material.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Material Production

Powder-route material was produced by dry blending, followed by canning under vacuum and hot extrusion. The reinforcements used were (a) spherical Al₂O₃ (diameter ~ 10 μm), (b) angular Al₂O₃ (approximately cuboids of side about 10-15 μm) and (c) chopped "Saffil" fibre (~3 μm diameter), which became broken up during extrusion into lengths of aspect ratio about 4. The spherical alumina powder was manufactured by melting and in-flight refreezing of the angular powder, using plasma spray equipment. Inert gas atomized commercial purity aluminium powder with a mean diameter of ~30 μm was used for the matrix. In all cases, the as-extruded microstructure consisted of well-dispersed particles in a matrix consisting of fine grains, elongated in the extrusion direction. These were formed by deformation of the original Al powder particles, and no recrystallization had taken place. All the powder-route composites contained about 0.08% by volume of fine platelets (d ~ 50 nm, t ~ 10 nm) derived from the oxide skin on the Al powder, broken up and aligned during extrusion. These could be seen as fine oxide stringers located along the prior particle boundaries.

The infiltrated material was produced using Saffil preforms, containing a silica binder. The density was 0.4 Mg m⁻³, corresponding to about 10vol% alumina. After squeeze infiltration, the billets were extruded in order to align the alumina fibres. As the same extrusion conditions were used, a similar amount of fibre fracture occurred in both the powder-route and squeeze infiltrated material. The squeeze infiltrated material differed from the powder-route composites in containing virtually no fine oxide particles in the matrix.

2.2. Mechanical Testing

Tensile testing was carried out, under displacement control, on a Schenck 10 kN screw-driven machine at room temperature, and on a Mand 50 kN screw-driven machine with a cylindrical furnace at high temperatures. Cylindrical specimens were used, with a gauge length (parallel to the extrusion axis) of 20 mm and a diameter of 3.5 mm. The strain rate was 5 10⁻³ s⁻¹. Specimen strain was measured using an LVDT at room temperature, and with digital calipers at elevated temperature. Tests were periodically interrupted in order to measure any changes in specimen

density as the test progressed. Destructive tests were also carried out, to establish whether the thermal cycling inherent in the interrupted test was affecting the cavitation. This was not found to be the case.

2.3. Microstructural Examination

Specimens were examined using optical and SEM microscopy. In order to observe the cavities and fine oxide particles in the SEM, electropolishing was used, to minimise the surface damage during preparation. Struers A2 electrolyte was employed, with polishing for 10 s at 18 V and final etching for 7 s at 13 V. Specimens were given a coating of gold and examined with a low accelerating voltage of about 8 kV.

2.4. Density Measurements

In order to monitor cavitation, specimen density was measured periodically during the tensile tests using an Archimedean technique. A Sartorius RC210P microbalance with a sensitivity of $\pm 10 \mu\text{g}$ was used. A high density fluorocarbon was used as the immersion fluid. Using this method, changes in specimen density of $\sim 0.05\%$ could be measured reliably. It was found that the as-extruded specimens contained zero porosity, within the accuracy limits imposed by the precision to which the densities and volume fractions of the constituents were known. The void content in the gauge length of strained specimens was calculated by making a correction for the unstrained volume beyond the specimen shoulders. In this way the evolution of cavities with plastic strain could be observed.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Metallographic Observation of Cavities

Cavities almost invariably formed at the matrix/reinforcement interfaces, in the direction of the applied stress. On examining the distribution of voids, it could be seen that in specimens tested at room temperature, they formed throughout the gauge length, growing to a stable hemispherical shape. Little necking was observed. Specimens strained at higher temperature, however, showed negligible cavitation remote from the vicinity of the fracture surface, with practically all the voids localised in the necked region.

For specimens tested at room temperature, favoured sites for cavitation were at the ends of elongated particles with planar ends oriented parallel to the stress axis. However, as test temperature increased, particle angularities were observed to be increasingly favoured sites. Figure 1 shows micrographs comparing typical voids at angular particles after testing at room temperature and 350°C . In 20% alumina composites, voids also tended to form where there was clustering of particles. This is attributed to the high triaxial constraint on the matrix in such regions. All reinforcements showed some examples of voids forming as a result of cracked particles. This appeared to be independent of test temperature, suggesting that reinforcement cracking had occurred during fabrication rather than during the subsequent testing.

3.2. Effect of Reinforcement Shape and Volume Fraction

In general it was observed that the onset of cavitation is delayed with increasing test temperature, due to the greater ductility of the matrix. This is demonstrated in Figure 2, which shows void content data for material containing spherical reinforcement at two volume fractions. However, once cavitation has begun during high temperature testing, the void content rises quickly with further straining and failure soon follows. This suggests that void growth and coalescence are rapid at high temperature, particularly when account is taken of the observation that voids are essentially confined to the necked region. Room temperature test data indicated that void contents increased significantly, and incubation strain decreased, as the reinforcement content is raised. This trend was not observed at higher temperatures, where specimens with different

reinforcement contents showed very similar cavitation behaviour, and overall void contents were lower. This can be explained in terms of favoured void nucleation sites. Microstructural observations have confirmed that at higher temperature voids tend to be formed at angularities rather than flat surfaces. If this is the case then the volume of an individual void at high temperature is likely to be smaller than at low temperature, thus reducing the total void content and hence observable difference between different volume fractions.

In Figure 3 void content data are shown for angular and spherical reinforcement at room temperature and 350°C. Angular reinforcement clearly leads to higher void contents than spherical at both temperatures. The overall void content decreases at higher temperature in both cases. Again the favouring of angularities as void nucleation sites will result in a reduction in cavity volume. At room temperature, where voids form at elongated particles with flat ends, the spherical reinforcement leads to lower void contents, since no elongated particles are present. However, interfaces are present which are approximately flat (particularly for large particles), so that void levels are low but not negligible. The high temperature data for spherical reinforcement, on the other hand, indicate very low void contents, up to strains where failure is imminent. This is consistent with the importance of elongation and sharp corners as cavitation sites at high temperature. The voids which did form are probably associated with cracked particles or clusters.

3.3. Effect of Processing Route

Microstructural examination of specimens strained at 350°C revealed that voids tended to form in regions where the reinforcement was clustered, or where a fibre was misaligned, thus producing an angularity parallel to the applied stress, see Figure 4. This is consistent with the preferred nucleation sites observed with the particulate reinforcement.

Void content data for powder- and cast-route 10vol% short fibre MMCs are compared in Figure 4. At room temperature, the powder-route material shows greater levels of cavitation than the cast material, although both contain similar void contents near the fracture surface at final failure. This can be explained in terms of the interfacial bond strength being higher in the cast material, which might result in a larger plastic strain being required to initiate cavitation. The high stability of the voids in the powder material may be related to the presence of fine aligned oxide stringers. While these probably lower the interfacial bond strength, they may also act to delay final void coalescence by inhibiting lateral growth. At 350°C, as with the particulate powder-route material, the onset of cavitation in the cast composites is delayed. It can also be seen that the powder-route material fails at a much lower plastic strain than the infiltrated, while both have similar void contents at failure. Again, this may be traced to an effect of the fine oxide stringers. These decrease the interfacial bond strength in the powder material, as at room temperature, but at elevated temperature they are unable to stabilise the voids and failure rapidly ensues.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The onset of cavitation is delayed at higher temperature.
- 2) Favoured void nucleation sites change from flattish surfaces of reinforcement particles to angularities as test temperature is increased. Void levels therefore tend to be very low with spherical reinforcement at high temperatures.
- 3) The difference in void content as reinforcement content is raised becomes less pronounced with increasing temperature.
- 4) The presence of oxide stringers in the matrix promotes cavitation at all temperatures. At room temperature they also stabilise the voids, preventing rapid coalescence and failure. This stabilising effect is reduced as test temperature is increased, leading to reduced ductility for powder-route material.

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Figure 3. Void content data comparing CP Al powder-route 10vol% angular and spherical particulate reinforcements at (a) 20°C and (b) 350°C.

Figure 4. CP Al 10vol% short fibre Alumina casting-route MMC showing typical void nucleation site at high temperature.

Figure 5. Void content data for powder-route and cast-route 10vol% short fibre MMC at (a) 20°C and (b) 350°C.